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TINNITUS: THE PHANTOM SOUND (PART V) PSYCHOLOGICAL ASPECTS – VOLUME 2

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In this bulletin we will continue on from volume 1, published in December 2025, which discussed psychological aspects related to tinnitus. We invite you to read the previous bulletins on tinnitus so that the current reading is more fruitful.

TINNITUS AND SLEEP: NIGHTS IN WAKEFULNESS

Insomnia is one of the most recurrent complaints among people with chronic tinnitus. The constant presence of sound prevents the brain from properly activating the relaxation mechanisms necessary for the transition from wakefulness to sleep. The absence of silence in the internal environment – even when the external environment is calm – can cause a state of persistent physiological arousal (Andersson et al., 2009).

In addition, nighttime anxiety and the fear of "not being able to sleep" generate a negative anticipation that, in itself, already delays the onset of sleep. Insomnia leads to an increase in oxidative stress, hormonal imbalances, and worsening of the perception of tinnitus itself – forming another vicious cycle.

MEMORY AND ATTENTION DEFICITS: AN OVERLOADED BRAIN

Studies using neuropsychological tests indicate that patients with severe tinnitus may have subtle but real deficits in executive functions such as working memory, selective attention, and processing speed (Trevis et al., 2016).

These cognitive changes are not directly caused by tinnitus itself, but by the brain's continuous effort to deal with it. The mind needs to allocate attentional resources to monitor, control, or avoid sound – which consumes mental energy and reduces the ability to focus on other tasks. It is as if the brain is always running a program in the background, consuming precious resources.

The emotional impact of tinnitus also contributes to:

- Ruminative thoughts;
- High stress;
- Fragmented sounds.

Which all negatively affect cognitive functioning.

As a result, the patient finds themselves more distracted, forgetful, and mentally exhausted – which further fuels frustration.

BRAIN SCARS: TINNITUS AS A PERSISTENT BRAIN STATE

Neuroscientifically, tinnitus is understood as the result of a cortical reorganization: when there is peripheral hearing loss, the brain tries to "compensate" for this absence of stimulus by increasing the sensitivity of the central auditory areas. This phenomenon, called central gain, can end up generating spontaneous neuronal activity – the "sound" of tinnitus (Eggermont & Roberts, 2015).

The problem is not only auditory. Tinnitus begins to recruit brain areas of attention (parietal cortex), emotional meaning and value (limbic system), and salience control (default mode network). This turns it into a multidimensional psychophysiological experience, which cannot be "turned off" simply with an earplug.

Even with advances in treatment strategies, there is still no definitive solution that guarantees the complete elimination of subjective tinnitus. However, some methods can help reduce discomfort and improve quality of life. It is estimated that approximately 1–3% of the population suffers from tinnitus severe enough to cause emotional and functional impairment.

Related emotional reactions are not unique to tinnitus. People with hyperacusis (increased tolerance to sounds) or misophonia (intense aversion to specific sounds) also report a variety of emotional discomfort whenever they perceive internal sounds or are exposed to external triggers. In these cases, the following may occur:

- Anxiety;
- Depression or sadness;
- Persistent irritability;
- Feelings of hopelessness in the face of sounds;
- Feelings of powerlessness or loss of control;
- Stress flare-ups;
- Anger, hostility, or even panic;
- Feeling of threat or lack of a way out;
- Impatience, repulsion and, in some cases, even resentment towards the sounds or situations that trigger them.

Interestingly, the severity of these symptoms is not directly related to the physical properties of the sound, such as its intensity or frequency. Research suggests that the most relevant factor is the meaning that sound has for the individual and the impact it has on their life.

For example, studies with tinnitus patients have shown that perceived sound intensity is not directly related to the severity of depressive symptoms. What really determines the level of distress is how much the patient feels that the sound interferes with their daily life, activities, and well-being. Similar results have been observed in studies on hyperacusis: the level of psychological distress cannot be explained by the auditory discomfort threshold alone.

These findings reinforce a central premise of cognitive theory, which holds that it is not events or stimuli that generate our emotions, but rather our interpretation of them.

With this logic, it is common for distorted automatic thoughts to appear, feeding the cycle of pain. Among the main ones are:

- **Catastrophizing, with reflections such as:**

“I can't bear to live like this.”

“This sound will drive me crazy.”

“My sensitivity will take me away from the world.”

- **Hasty conclusions, such as:**

“If a sound bothers me so much, it must be damaging my hearing.”

- **Self-blame, manifested by ideas such as:**

“The responsibility for all of this is mine.”

“If I can't stand certain sounds, there must be something very wrong with me.”

- **Judgment of others and generalizations, such as:**

“ People make noise just to annoy me.”

“ Those who make noise don't care about others.”

These distorted thoughts not only increase suffering, but also favor dysfunctional behaviors – especially those of excessive avoidance and protection. These are attempts to minimize discomfort, but in the long run, they end up perpetuating the problem.

Among the most observed behaviors are:

- **With tinnitus:** avoiding quiet environments for fear that the internal sound will become unbearable.
- **In hyperacusis:** restricting going out, using ear protectors excessively, and reducing social interaction.
- **In misophonia:** adopting strategies such as listening to music to mask unpleasant sounds, quickly leaving places, or reacting aggressively – verbally imitating a sound.

Although these attitudes provide momentary relief, they end up reinforcing in the brain the idea that sound is a real threat. This prevents the development of a process called habituation, which occurs when the nervous system learns to ignore repetitive and harmless stimuli.

Research using functional neuroimaging confirms that there is hyperactivity in brain areas linked to the regulation of emotions – such as the amygdala, the insula, and the limbic system – in individuals affected by tinnitus, hyperacusis, and misophonia. When exposed to the sounds that bother them, these people have an exaggerated emotional response, revealing an alteration in the processing of these stimuli.

This causes the brain to treat the sound as something threatening, increasing its perception, making it more intrusive and almost impossible to ignore. **As a consequence, difficulties arise such as:**

- Excessive and involuntary attention to tinnitus;
- Inability to filter noise in the environment (characteristic of hyperacusis);
- Intense and automatic emotional reactions to trigger sounds (in misophonia).

This pattern also prevents the brain from activating its natural habituation mechanisms, keeping the sound constantly in evidence and, consequently, perpetuating discomfort.

Understanding tinnitus as a multifactorial phenomenon is the first step towards a more compassionate and effective therapeutic approach. The suffering it causes is not only in the sound, but in the interaction between individual predispositions, personality traits, emotional experiences, and biological states.

VULNERABILITIES AND AWARENESS: WHY DOES TINNITUS AFFECT SOME MORE THAN OTHERS?

Most people with hearing loss do not develop chronic disabling tinnitus. This indicates that there are modulating factors involved – and they are usually psychological and neurobiological.

People with a history of emotional trauma, high levels of chronic stress, or personality disorders tend to develop a more intense brain response to tinnitus. Higher rates of distress are also observed in individuals with low emotional resilience, intolerance to ambiguity, and obsessive-compulsive traits.

In addition, the subjective experience of helplessness in the face of tinnitus ("I can't do anything", "this will last forever") is directly related to the severity of the symptoms. Psychoeducation, at this point, can act as a central therapeutic tool, helping the patient understand what is happening to their body and mind – and what can be done to reduce the impact.

THE ROLE OF PSYCHOTHERAPEUTIC APPROACHES: THE BRAIN THAT LEARNS, THE MIND THAT ADAPTS

Among the most effective treatments for tinnitus with associated emotional distress is Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT). Evidence from randomized controlled trials and retrospective uncontrolled studies indicates that CBT is an effective and well-accepted intervention in the management of tinnitus. Studies show that CBT can significantly reduce the perceived intensity of tinnitus, improve quality of life, and decrease symptoms of anxiety and depression (Cima et al., 2012).

This is because CBT acts directly on the brain mechanisms of interpretation, cognitive reappraisal, restructuring of automatic thoughts, and modulation of attention. By changing the way the patient reacts to the sound, the brain gradually relearns not to assign it so much emotional weight – allowing habituation.

Other complementary approaches, such as mindfulness, neurofeedback, biofeedback techniques, attention training, and acceptance and commitment therapy (ACT), have also shown benefits, especially when associated with emotional regulation, sleep, and self-care practices.

Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT) is currently considered the approach with the greatest scientific support for the management of tinnitus associated with emotional distress. Unlike sound-centered approaches, CBT works with the thoughts, emotions, beliefs, and behaviors that maintain or amplify the negative perception of tinnitus.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF COGNITIVE-BEHAVIORAL THERAPY IN TINNITUS

The cognitive model assumes that the way we interpret an event (in this case, tinnitus) directly influences our emotional and behavioral response. In tinnitus, the initially neutral sound is interpreted as threatening, uncontrollable, or unbearable, which activates a state of continuous alarm. This state feeds emotions such as anxiety, anger, sadness, and hopelessness – in addition to making it difficult to get used to.

CBT seeks to identify and modify these dysfunctional patterns, focusing on:

- Cognitive restructuring (changing negative automatic thoughts);
- Attention training (tinnitus defocusing);
- Coping strategies and tolerance;
- Reduction of avoidance or hypervigilance behaviors;
- Emotional stabilization;

SCIENTIFIC EVIDENCE: WHAT DO THE STUDIES SAY?

- 01. Cima et al.** (2012) conducted a randomized controlled trial published in *The Lancet*, with 492 participants, comparing personalized CBT with standard care (information and support). The group that received CBT showed significant improvement in tinnitus-related distress, anxiety, depression, and functional impact scores, with lasting effects at a 12-month follow-up.
- 02. Martinez-Devesa et al.** conducted a systematic review of the Cochrane Library and concluded that CBT improves the quality of life of people with tinnitus, especially in the emotional domains. Although it does not alter the objective perception of sound, it reduces discomfort and subjective suffering.
- 03. Zenner et al.** (2017) propose an integrative neuropsychological model where tinnitus is seen as a brain network disorder. CBT, in this context, intervenes on the salience network and the limbic system, helping to reframe tinnitus and reduce its emotional load.
- 04.** In a recent meta-analysis, **Fuller et al.** (2020) confirmed that CBT significantly reduces the severity of tinnitus symptoms, especially compared to passive treatments such as medications or counseling alone.

PRACTICAL APPLICATION: HOW COGNITIVE-BEHAVIORAL THERAPY WORKS IN THE TINNITUS PATIENT

A typical CBT protocol for tinnitus includes 6 to 12 sessions, tailored to the intensity of distress and comorbidities.

Key elements include:

- **Psychoacoustic and neuropsychological education:** explanation of the mechanisms of tinnitus, habituation, brain plasticity, and the role of emotions.
- **Mapping dysfunctional thoughts:** for example, "I'll never have peace again", "This sound will drive me crazy", "Nobody understands".
- **Cognitive restructuring:** replacing catastrophic thoughts with more realistic and functional interpretations.
- **Attention training:** focus shifting techniques, divided attention, exercises with ambient sounds or neutral sounds.
- **Stress management and emotional regulation:** diaphragmatic breathing, mindfulness, self-compassion.
- **Gradual exposure to previously avoided sounds:** when there is also associated hyperacusis or misophonia.

INTEGRATION WITH NEUROSCIENCE

CBT directly modulates brain areas involved in the emotional reaction to sound, such as the dorsolateral prefrontal cortex, the amygdala, and the anterior cingulate cortex. The repeated practice of cognitive reappraisal and emotional regulation favors desensitization of the limbic system, allowing the sound of tinnitus to be perceived as irrelevant – even if it is still present.

LIMITS AND CONSIDERATIONS

CBT does not promise to eliminate the sound of tinnitus, but it has proven effective in reducing psychological distress and improving functionality. It is most effective when applied to patients with relevant emotional distress, especially those with traits of anxiety, OCD, or mild to moderate depression. It can be combined with other approaches such as TRT, sound devices, or pharmacotherapy if needed.

Quiz: Buzzing and Psychological Aspects - module 2

1. What is the main reason, according to the text, why chronic tinnitus can cause memory and attention deficits?

- a) Cognitive distortions, such as catastrophizing, directly cause attention and memory deficits.
- b) Tinnitus, by itself, damages the brain areas responsible for memory and attention.
- c) The brain's continuous effort to deal with sound consumes attentional and energetic resources, overloading the mind and making it difficult to focus on other tasks.
- d) The constant sound of tinnitus prevents the brain from activating the relaxation mechanisms necessary for sleep, leading to insomnia and, consequently, memory loss.
- e) Tinnitus causes the brain to treat the sound as something threatening, increasing its perception and making it more intrusive.

2. What does the text describe as 'central gain' in the context of tinnitus neuroscience?

- a) The brain's ability to increase the intensity of perceived sound, even if peripheral hearing loss is minimal.
- b) A brain adaptation process that allows the individual to ignore the sound of tinnitus over time.
- c) The ability of Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy to reduce psychological distress in patients with chronic tinnitus.
- d) A phenomenon of cortical reorganization in which the brain, upon detecting a loss of peripheral stimulus, increases the sensitivity of the central auditory areas, generating the sound of tinnitus.
- e) Hyperactivity in brain areas linked to the regulation of emotions, such as the amygdala and insula.

3. A tinnitus patient reports the following thought: 'If I can't stand certain sounds, there must be something very wrong with me.' According to the text, what kind of cognitive distortion does this statement represent?

- a) Self-blame
- b) Hasty conclusion
- c) Rumination
- d) Judgment of others and generalization
- e) Catastrophizing

4. What is the main objective of Cognitive-Behavioral Therapy (CBT) in the treatment of tinnitus, according to the text?

- a) Reduce psychological distress and improve quality of life by allowing the brain to get used to sound, even if it is still present.
- b) Increase the patient's tolerance to loud sounds to prevent hyperacusis.
- c) Intervene directly in the brain's salience network so that the sound is immediately ignored.
- d) Eliminate the sound of tinnitus in a guaranteed way.
- e) Medicate the patient to alter neurotransmitter levels.

5. According to the text, the severity of the emotional conditions associated with tinnitus, hyperacusis and misophonia is more related to which factor?

- a) The intensity and frequency of the perceived sound.
 - b) The individual's chronic stress level, which directly causes tinnitus.
 - c) Low emotional resilience, which prevents the patient from accepting the condition.
 - d) The history of emotional trauma in childhood.
 - e) The meaning that sound takes on for the individual and the impact it generates in their daily life.
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Correct quiz answers

1. Correct answer: c
2. Correct answer: d
3. Correct answer: d
4. Correct answer: d
5. Correct answer: d

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